

Romanchuk L.I.**Tarnavska S.I.****Hresko A.M.****Dushka B.A.***Bukovyna State Medical University*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15255943>**EXTRAGULAR MANIFESTATIONS OF HELICOBACTER PYLORI: FOCUS ON THE HEPATOBILIARY SYSTEM IN CHILDREN****Abstract**

The article highlights modern ideas about the participation of *Helicobacter pylori* in the development of hepatobiliary system pathology in children. The data of modern studies on the association of infection with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, cholecystitis, biliary dyskinesia are presented. The pathogenetic mechanisms, diagnostic methods and treatment approaches are described. The need for further studies to confirm cause-and-effect relationships is indicated.

Keywords: *Helicobacter pylori*, hepatobiliary system, children, nonalcoholic fatty liver disease, dyskinesia, cholecystitis

Hepatobiliary diseases in childhood are an urgent problem in pediatric practice, which largely determines the quality of life of patients and the risk of chronicity of processes in adulthood. In recent years, the role of infectious agents in the development of these pathologies, in particular *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*), has attracted considerable attention. Traditionally, this bacterium is associated with gastroduodenal pathology, but there is a growing body of data on its potential role in liver and biliary tract lesions, which requires further study, especially in the pediatric population.

Materials and methods. The paper reviews current literature (2020–2024) from international databases PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science. The analysis includes systematic reviews, meta-analyses, and clinical studies on the association of *H. pylori* with nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), cholecystitis, cholangitis, and other forms of hepatobiliary pathology in children. The main mechanisms of pathogenesis, diagnostic approaches, and efficacy of therapy are evaluated.

Results. According to recent data, *H. pylori* is detected not only in the stomach, but also in liver and gallbladder tissues. Liu C. et al. in a meta-analysis found that *H. pylori*-positive status is associated with an increased risk of developing NAFLD - 1.3–1.5 times more often than in uninfected patients [2]. Heydari K. and colleagues showed that infection contributes to metabolic disorders, including dyslipidemia, insulin resistance and fatty liver [3]. Chen X. et al. found that *H. pylori* activates a systemic inflammatory response by increasing the levels of IL-1 β , IL-6 and TNF- α , which contributes to the progression of liver fibrosis [4]. In some cases, *H. pylori* is associated with cholecystitis and even stone formation, which is probably associated with changes in the rheological properties of bile and impaired bile outflow [5].

In clinical practice, children with *H. pylori*-associated liver lesions may have nonspecific symptoms - periodic pain in the right hypochondrium, dyspeptic manifestations, increased fatigue. The infection often has an

asymptomatic course, which complicates early diagnosis.

The main methods for detecting infection remain a breath test, determination of *H. pylori* antigen in feces, serological studies and endoscopy with biopsy. In case of confirmation, eradication therapy (triple or quadruple therapy) is used, the effectiveness of which in the pediatric population is 70–80% [6].

Conclusions. *Helicobacter pylori* may play an important role in the development of hepatobiliary diseases in children. Its ability to colonize not only the stomach, but also the liver and biliary tract, with subsequent activation of the immune response and chronic inflammation, is a promising direction for research. Early detection and adequate treatment of the infection can reduce the risk of developing chronic hepatobiliary diseases and improve the long-term prognosis of patients.

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